

**Derivatives of Salicylic Acid. Part VIII. Interaction
of Thionyl Chloride with Esters of Hydroxy
Aromatic Acids in Presence of Finely Divided
Copper. Part III. Synthesis and Constitu-
tion of 3:3'-Carbomethoxy-4:4'-hydroxy-
5:5'-methyldiphenyl Sulphide and its
6:6'-Methyl Analogue.**

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Methyl esters of 3-methyl- and 4-methylsalicylic acids were chosen to continue the work described previously (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1933, 2,128) and it has been found that whereas methyl 5-methylsalicylate does not react, its 3-methyl isomer reacts with difficulty giving a poor yield while the 4-methyl analogue reacts easily giving a good yield.

Though both positions 3 and 5 are favoured by the directing influences of OH and COOH groups in salicylic acid yet the 5-isomer is generally the major product and in sulphonation 5-sulphosalicylic acid alone is obtained. It is interesting to note, in the present investigation, that though the original influence is increased by the presence of the Me group in methyl 4-methylsalicylate, the 5-derivative only is obtained. When the 5-position is occupied by the Me group as in methyl 5-methylsalicylate no condensation could be effected, while in the case of 3-methyl isomer the 5-derivative was obtained with difficulty, indicating that the Me group hinders the directive influences of OH and COOH groups to the position *meta* to itself ; and that the thio group prefers to enter the *para* position to OH group.

As for the mechanism of the reaction it has been found that the presence of copper as a catalyst is necessary, since the reaction is inhibited by the presence of a COOH group. The rôle of copper in the reaction is two-fold. The following series of equations illustrate the reaction :—

Reaction of thionyl chloride with bivalent metals (Mellor, "Treatise of Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. X, 662). supports (i). The fact that the sulphur monochloride and sulphur dichloride do not react with the esters without the presence of copper or cuprous chloride, supports (ii) and (v). That the anhydrous copper chloride does not catalyse the reaction, but it is catalysed by (a) the hydrated copper chloride, (b) anhydrous copper chloride with traces of water, or (c) anhydrous copper chloride with SO_2 initially passed in the mixture, supports equations (iii) and (iv).

The constitution of the products formed by the action of thionyl chloride on methyl 4-methylsalicylate and methyl 3-methylsalicylate was proved to be 3:3'-carbomethoxy-4:4'-hydroxy-6:6'-methyl-diphenyl sulphide and 3:3'-carbomethoxy-4:4'-hydroxy-5:5'-methyl-diphenyl sulphide by the action of dilute nitric acid on their respective carboxylic acids, when known 4-methyl-5-nitrosalicylic and 3-methyl-5-nitrosalicylic acids were formed. Concentrated nitric acid, however, reacted with these acids giving 2:4:6-trinitro-3-methylphenol and 4:5:6-trinitro-2-methylphenol.

EXPERIMENTAL.

3:3'-Carbomethoxy-4:4'-hydroxy-6:6'-methyldiphenyl sulphide.—To a mixture of methyl 4-methylsalicylate (30 g.) and thionyl chloride (50 g.) copper dust (20 g.) was gradually added when dense fumes of sulphur dioxide and hydrogen chloride were evolved. The mixture was protected from moisture by fitting the flask with a cork carrying a tube twice bent at right angles and kept at room temperature overnight and then warmed on a water-bath for about an hour. After extracting with chloroform and filtering the copper dust, the filtrate was evaporated and the solid repeatedly crystallised from dilute acetic acid when colourless needles, m. p. 162° , were obtained. It is soluble in chloroform, benzene, acetic acid, carbon disulphide, acetone, ethyl alcohol; insoluble in petroleum ether and carbon tetrachloride and gives bluish violet coloration with ferric chloride solution. (Found: S, 8.87; Equiv, 181.2. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6\text{S}$ requires S, 8.84 per cent. Equiv., 181).

The *diacetyl* derivative, prepared by the action of warm acetic anhydride in presence of a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid, crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 132°. (Found: S, 7.06. $C_{22}H_{22}O_8S$ requires S, 7.17 per cent).

The *dibenzoyl* derivative, prepared in pyridine solution and warming the mixture on a water-bath for about 3 hours, crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 140°. (Found: S, 5.48. $C_{32}H_{26}O_8S$ requires S, 5.31 per cent).

The *dicarbamido* derivative.—A mixture of the carbomethoxy compound (5 g.) and liquor ammonia (100 c. c.) was shaken for about 8 hours and the solid obtained after the evaporation of the liquid was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in gritty flakes, m. p. 280° (decomp.). It is insoluble in alcohol, chloroform, acetone and glacial acetic acid. (Found: N, 8.19 ; S, 9.47. $C_{16}H_{16}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 8.48 ; S, 9.64 per cent).

3 : 3'-*Carboxy-4 : 4'-hydroxy-6 : 6'-methyldiphenyl sulphide*.—The above ester (10 g.) was treated with sodium hydroxide (10%, 100 c. c.) and boiled for about 2 hours. The solid obtained on acidification with hydrochloric acid was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colourless plates, m. p. 260° (decomp.). It is difficultly soluble in chloroform and benzene ; insoluble in petroleum ether and soluble in acetone, acetic acid, ethyl alcohol and gives bluish violet coloration with ferric chloride solution. (Found: S, 9.75 ; Equiv., 167.3. $C_{16}H_{14}O_6S$ requires S, 9.58 per cent. Equiv., 167.0).

The *diacetyl* derivative was prepared in the usual manner, m. p. 199°. (Found: S, 7.53. $C_{20}H_{18}O_8S$ requires, S, 7.65 per cent).

The *dibenzoyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 188°. It is soluble in common solvents but insoluble in benzene and petroleum ether. (Found: S, 5.79. $C_{30}H_{22}O_8S$ requires S, 5.9 per cent).

The *dimethoxy* derivative was prepared by methylating with dimethylsulphate and crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 232°. (Found: S, 8.78. $C_{18}H_{18}O_6S$ requires S, 8.84 per cent).

3 : 3'-*Carboxy-4 : 4'-hydroxy-5 : 5'-bromomethyl-6 : 6'-diphenyl sulphide*.—The above substance was dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid (200 c. c.) and bromine (5.5 g.) in acetic acid (15 c. c.) was gradually added. The brominated compound which separated on cooling was crystallised from hot glacial acetic acid in colourless needles, m. p. 267° (decomp.). It is insoluble in benzene, petroleum ether;

sparingly soluble in chloroform, ethyl alcohol and acetic acid. (Found: Br, 32.43; S, 6.33. Equiv., 245.6. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6Br_2S$ requires Br, 32.52; S, 6.50 per cent. Equiv., 246.0).

4-Methyl-5-nitrosalicylic acid.—3:3'-Carboxy-4:4'-hydroxy-6:6'-methyldiphenyl sulphide was suspended in dilute nitric acid (20 c. c. concentrated acid and 80 c. c. water) and warmed till a clear solution was obtained. The solid precipitated on diluting the cold solution with much water was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 219°. (Found: N, 6.93. $C_8H_7O_5N$ requires N, 7.11 per cent). Borsche and Berkhout (*Annalen*, 1903, 330, 100) give m. p. 219°.

2:4:6-Trinitro-3-methylphenol.—When the original thioether (1 g.) was treated with concentrated nitric acid (10 c.c.) warmed a little and then diluted with water a solid compound was obtained which crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 108°. (Found: N, 16.96. $C_7H_5O_7N_3$ requires N, 17.28 per cent). Nölting and Salis (*Ber.*, 1881, 14, 987) give m. p. 105-6°.

3:3'-Carbomethoxy-4:4'-hydroxy-5:5'-methyldiphenyl sulphide.—This was prepared from methyl 3-methylsalicylate (30 g.) thionyl chloride (50 g.) and copper dust (20 g.) and isolated like its 6-methyl isomer; but in this case a pasty solid was obtained which was washed with petroleum ether and repeatedly crystallised from dilute acid in needles, m. p. 161°. It resembles its 6-methyl isomer in solubility and other properties. (Found: S, 8.8. Equiv., 182.3. $C_{18}H_{18}O_6S$ requires S, 18.84 per cent. Equiv., 181.0).

3:3'-Carboxy-4:4'-hydroxy-5:5'-methyldiphenyl sulphide.—It was obtained by hydrolysing the above ester with sodium hydroxide (10%, 100 c. c.). It crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colourless plates, m. p. 279° (decomp.). It resembles its 6-methyl isomer in solubility and other properties. (Found: S, 9.5; Equiv., 167.2. $C_{16}H_{14}O_6S$ requires S, 9.6 per cent. Equiv., 167.0). It gave 3-methyl-5-nitro-salicylic acid with dilute nitric acid. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m. p. 199°. (Found: N, 6.9, $C_8H_7O_5N$ requires N, 7.11 per cent). (Einhorn and Pfyl, *Annalen*, 1900, 311, 47; Borsche and Berkhout, *loc. cit.*) give m. p. 199°. Concentrated nitric acid gave 4:5:6-trinitro-2-methyl-phenol, m. p. 102°. (Found: N, 17.0. $C_7H_5O_7N_3$ requires N, 17.28 per cent) Nölting and Collin (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 270) and Sommer (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1903, ii, 67, 553) give m. p. 102°.